

Social Media and Social Interaction: Adversities and Advantages with Special Reference to Cyber Bullying

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Abstract

The present research entitled, “*Social media and social interaction: Adversities and advantages with special reference to cyber bullying*” investigates the effects of social media on social interaction among individuals in contemporary society with the rise of social media platforms such as whatsapp, facebook, instagram, and snapchat etc., There has been a significant shift in interaction and communication. The present research investigates the positive and negative effects of social media on interpersonal relationship, communication pattern and social behaviour. A descriptive as well as analytical design with a semi-structured questionnaire is utilised to understand the influence of social media usage on social interaction and communications at Manzini town in Eswatini. The respondents using social media expresses the positive impact of using social media like development of social contacts, increased IQ level and encouraging worldwide interaction with people and on the other hand those who highlighted negative impact view social media as waste of time, money and limits face-to-face interaction and communication skills, furthering cyber bullying and addiction. The challenge against privacy and security of the social media user leads to harassment or cyberbullying. The respondents recognise the effectiveness of intervention aimed at promoting safety and responsible social media. The present research provides a valuable insight into the benefits and drawbacks of social media encouraging researchers and policy makers to conduct further studies in developing strategies to mitigate the risks and promote healthy social media use.

Keywords: *Social media, Social interaction, Adversities, cyberbullying, impact.*

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Introduction

Social media has a momentous influence on communication and social interaction. It has changed the way people interact and connects with each other. The convenience in communication has unintended consequences such as reducing face-to-face interaction and declining emotional bonds between relatives and friends. In a way social media has given rise to new forms of communication such as messaging apps and video conferencing tools etc. Social media use has enormously increased in the past decades. There has been a rise in sites such as Facebook, X (formerly Twitter), WhatsApp and Instagram which has made it easier for people to connect with others, share information and ideas, keeping in touch with family and friends.

Hypothesis

H₁: Social media impacts the health of social media users.

H₂: Social media has enriched the communication momentum.

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Research Objectives

1. To analyse the effects of social media on the degree of communication.
2. To discuss the positive and negative impact of social media on life and interaction of its users.
3. To examine current scenario of cyber bullying and its containment.

Research Questions

1. What are the effects of social media on interpersonal relations?
2. What are the adversities and advantages of social media?

Significance of the Study

In today's digital age, social media has become an integral part of our daily lives. It has revolutionized the way we communicate and interact with each other both online and face to face. The present research intends to understand the changes taking place in medium of interaction and communication in society, which is significant in providing valuable insights into the benefits and drawbacks of social media use. It also helps to realise the potential risks associated with excessive use of social media, the risks like addiction to social media, cyberbullying, depression and social isolation.

Scope and Limitation of the Study

The study takes social media apps like whatsapp, instagram, facebook and X (formerly tweeter) users into consideration. Nowadays, whatsapp and facebook are the most frequently used social media networks and the messages and posts on such network has quite significant impact on developing an adapted perception of societal nature. It allows worldwide communication in real time and has facilitated the formation of online communities and relationships. It develops an attitude towards life and in contrast weakens the ever existing culture which is based on emotions and sentiments. The present study is limited to researching positive as well as negative aspects of social media on an individual's life, which is limited to Manzini town in Eswatini.

Review of Literature

Theories on Effects of Social Media on Social Interaction and Communication

This section of the literature review discusses the theories that constitute the theoretical framework to guide the study.

Social capital: offline and online

The social capital theory was first defined by (Bourdieu, 1986) as the aggregate of the actual or potential resources which are linked to possession of a durable network of institutionalized relationships of mutual acquaintance or recognition. According to (Martin, 2015) social capital theory contends that social relationships are resources that can lead to the development and accumulation of human capital. In evolutionary terms, social capital can be defined as any feature of a social relationship that yields reproductive benefits. The article further states that social networks provided the opportunity for the exchange of information, however the quality of information exchanged was largely based on the functional components of social capital, trust, and norms.

The internet has been linked both to increases and decreases in social capital. According to (Nicole B Ellison, 2007) internet use detracts from face-to-face time with others, which might diminish an individual's social capital. However, this perspective has received strong criticism, some researchers have claimed that online interaction may supplement or replace in person, mitigating any loss from time spent online.

Recently researchers have emphasized the importance of internet-based linkages for the formation of weak ties, which serve as the foundation of bridging social capital. The study further revealed that online

social network tools may be of utility for individuals who otherwise have difficulties forming and maintaining both strong and weak ties. The social capital theory guides the research study to the effects of social media on social interaction and communication by that social media platforms have transformed the way individuals connect, communicate and interact with one another, creating new opportunities for building and maintain social capital.

Empirical Studies

According to (Subramanian, 2017) one big concern surrounding social media impacts is communication overload, which basically means learning how to handle and make sense of this enormous information we acquire. The article states that there has been recent data suggesting that teens are pulling away from social media sites such as facebook and Instagram because it is just too much for them to handle.

Another negative effect of social media is lack of privacy, as interpersonal communication is changing, we are likely to share on social media the sort of information we might have previously shared privately face to face. The article by (Subramanian, 2017), further states the negativity surrounding social media is countered by positive influences, including the ability to communicate with more people across greater distances with an increased speed. Before social media, people were extremely limited in their means to interact with each other and were limited by the number of people they know in person. Social media networks allow us to share opinions with a far wider audience. Another big change is that nowadays there is no filter over the way we speak, in the past unless you spoke to people directly you had no way to get your message across regardless of your freedom of speech but now, we can use social media to get our messages out to thousands or even millions of people uncensored. Social media has also changed the way that we interact, mainly the way we have lost some of our social skills (Subramanian, 2017).

According (Els, 2020) beliefs that the relationship values and beliefs have changed due to social media, when talking about relationships it is not just romantic relationship, but this includes everyone that an individual has ever connected with at some point of their lives such as family, friends, and the relationship one has with themselves including the person you once argued with online. Anrita Els further states that for some reason people seem to value the opinions of online strangers more than the people who know and love them for who they are.

Social media has caused major damage to individuals face to face social skills, many people prefer online interaction because it is much easier, people can edit and delete whatever they say. The downside of social media is that the humanity of it all is missing, and the quality of people's relationships has reduced.

A research study conducted by (Davis, 2013) investigates the joint effects of interpersonal relationships and digital media use on adolescents' sense of identity. Questionnaires were administered to a sample of 2079 students (57% female) between the ages of 11 and 19 years ($M = 15.4$ years) attending one of seven secondary schools in Bermuda. The author found that mothers and friends play an important role in adolescents' lives, with both relationships contributing in positive ways to respondents' self-concept clarity. Further the results showed that mother relationship quality affected adolescent's self-concept clarity both directly and indirectly, through the positive impact it had on friendship quality. Friends also played a mediating role in relation to aspects of adolescent's digital media use, specifically the negative association detected between online identity expression and self-concept clarity was mediated partially by low friendship quality. Going online to communicate with one's friends appeared to play a more positive role in adolescents' sense of identity.

Methodology

To analyse the growing influences of the digital devices and social media on the interpersonal relationship a descriptive as well as analytical design with a semi-structured questionnaire is utilised to understand and attain the research objectives at Manzini town in Eswatini.

social media and provides statistical evidences of certain behaviours or attitudes related to social media use.

Data Type and Sources

Both the qualitative and quantitative approaches are used to study social media and interaction. The research involves gathering data through interviews, observations and other non-numeric methods. These approaches can be useful in exploring individuals' experiences and perspectives on social media use and communication. This form of data collection falls under primary data because it is the information collected directly by the researcher and along with the secondary sources like books, thesis, articles and government websites are also utilized for statistical as well as theoretical understanding.

Data Analyzing and Interpretation

Profile of the Respondents

Table 1. Age-Wise Distribution of the Respondents

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	18 to 25	12	37.5	37.5	37.5
	25 to 30	11	34.4	34.4	71.9
	30 to 35	04	12.5	12.5	84.4
	35 to 40	05	15.6	15.6	100.0
	Total	32	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field survey, 2024

As depicted in Table No. 1, out of 32 respondents 37.5 percent of the respondents are in the age categories of 18 to 25 years, 34.4 percent are between the age of 25 to 30 years old, in addition 12.5 percent are 30 to 35 years and 15.6 percent fall within the age category of 35 to 40 years old. From the above table it can be deduced that a majority of the respondents are either in the age group of 18 to 25 years or 25 to 30.

Table 2. Sex-Wise Distribution of the Respondents

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Male	16	50.0	50.0	50.0
	Female	16	50.0	50.0	100.0
	Total	32	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field survey, 2024

The above table shows the sex composition of the respondents. It reveals that 50 percent of the respondents are females and 50 percent are males. This was deliberately done to ensure fair representation of both genders.

Table 3. Occupational Distribution of the Respondents

Occupation		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Student	15	46.9	46.9	46.9
	Self employed	08	25.0	25.0	71.9
	Business	02	06.3	06.3	78.1
	Professional	04	12.5	12.5	90.6
	Not Applicable	03	09.4	09.4	100.0
	Total	32	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field survey, 2024; Note: Not applicable includes unemployed

The above distribution table (3) shows that out of 32 respondents 46.88 percent of them are students, 25 percent of them are self-employed, 6.25 percent of them are in the business sector, 12.5 percent are professional and 9.38 percent of them fall in not applicable category. This reflects that many of the respondents are students, followed by self-employed.

Social Media

Table 4. Use of Social Media by the Respondents

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	31	97	97.0	97.0
	No	01	03	03.0	100.0
	Total	32	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field survey, 2024

The above table (4) displays the results of respondents when asked if they use social media or not. Out of 32 of the respondents, 97 percent of them use social media and 3 percent of the respondents do not use social media.

Table 5. Nature of Impact of Social Media on Social Interaction and Communication

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Positive impact	11	34.4	34.4	34.4
	Negative impact	03	09.4	09.4	43.8
	Neutral	18	56.3	56.3	100.0
	Total	32	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field survey, 2024

Figure 2. Impact of Social Media on Social Interaction and Communication

The above table indicates that 34.4 percent out of 32 respondents felt that social media has a positive impact on social interaction and communication, 9.4 percent of the respondents stated that social media has a negative impact on social interaction and communication and the last 18 56.3 percent of respondents thought that social media had a neutral effect on social interaction and communication.

Table 5a. Positive Impacts of Social Media (N = 11)

Sl.No.	Positive Aspects	Frequency	Percentage
1	Develops social contacts	03	27.30
2	Increase IQ level	04	36.40
3	Worldwide Interaction with people	06	54.50
4	Foster new relationship & strengthening existing ones	04	36.40
5	Enhanced information	07	63.60
6	Career advancement	06	54.50
7	Shapes interpersonal relationships	04	36.40

Source: Field survey, 2024

The above table No.5 (a) illustrates that out of 32 respondents 27.30 percent of them expressed that social media has a positive impact of developing social contacts, 36. percent of them said, it increases IQ level, 54.50 percent believed it leads to worldwide interaction with people, 36.4 percent of them felt that it fosters new relationship and strengthens existing ones, 63.6 percent stated that social media leads to enhanced information, 54.5 percent of them leads to career advancement and the last 36.4 percent of them shapes interpersonal relationships.

The positive impact of social media is that, it leads to enhanced information, career advancement and worldwide interaction with people. This is due to the provision of easy access to people through social media networks.

Table 5b. Negative Impact of Social Media (N = 03)

Sl.No.	Negative Aspects	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Waste of time	02	66.7
2	Waste of money	02	66.7
3	Limits f2f contacts with relatives and friends	03	100
4	Cyber bullying	03	100
5	Addiction	03	100
6	Promotes laziness	01	33.0

Source: Field survey, 2024

Table No. 5 (b) shows the negative aspects of social media on social interaction and communication. Out of 32 respondents only 3 respondents fall in the given category who expressed that social media is a waste of time, money, limits face to face contacts with relatives and friends and cent percent of the respondents reveal cyber bullying and addiction.

Table 6. Various Roles of Social Media (N = 32)

Sl.No.	Opinion	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Social media has made communication more instant and accessible, allowing people to connect with each other from anywhere in the world at any time	21	70
2	Social media has introduced new forms of communication, such as emojis and memes, in which can convey emotions and ideas in a more concise and visual way	09	30
3	Social media has created new challenges for privacy and security, as people may share sensitive information or be vulnerable to online harassment or cyberbullying	12	40

Source: Field survey, 2024

Table No. 6 depicts, 70 percent of the respondents felt that social media has made communication more instant and accessible, allowing people to connect with each other from anywhere in the world at any

time, 30 percent of the respondents stated that social media has introduced new forms of communication, such as emojis and memes, in which they convey emotions and ideas in a more concise and visual way and lastly 40 percent felt that social media has created new challenges for privacy and security, as people may share sensitive information or be vulnerable to online harassment or cyberbullying.

H₂: Social Media leads to enriched communication momentum, is tested by crosstabulation of Table 5 and Table 6, using Chi-square test.

Table 7. Social Media User and Enriched Communication Momentum

			Social Media enriched communication momentum		Total
			No	Yes	
Social Media User	No	00	01	01	
	Yes	09	20	29	
Total		09	21	30	

Table 8. Chi-Square Tests

	Value	Df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (1-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	.443 ^a	1	.506		
Fisher's Exact Test				1.000	.700
Linear-by-Linear Association	.429	1	.513		
N of Valid Cases	30				

Significance

Asymptotic Significance (2-sided) (p-value = 0.506): This is the most relevant value for interpreting the test. It represents the probability of getting a chi-square statistic as extreme or more extreme than what you observed, assuming there's truly no association (null hypothesis is true).

A high p-value (greater than 0.05, as in this case) suggests the observed difference is likely due to chance and doesn't provide strong evidence against the null hypothesis

*This suggests that, **H₀: Social media has no relation with enriched communication momentum** is true and accepted and **H₂: Social media has enriched the communication momentum** is rejected.*

Interpretation

In simpler terms, the data shows some variation in how social media use relates to communication momentum, but this variation is not statistically significant.

Table 9. Opinion Regarding Dishonesty on Social Media

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	25	78.1	78.1	78.1
	No	07	21.9	21.9	100.0
	Total	32	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field survey, 2024

Figure 3. Dishonesty on Social Media

Table 9 illustrates the opinion of respondents when asked about the degree in which people are dishonest in social media. Out of 32 participants, 78.1 percent of them stated that people are dishonest on social media and 21.88 percent stated that people are not dishonest on social media. This indicates that a majority of the respondents believe that in their experience people tend to be less honest when it comes to social media.

Table 10. Opinion Regarding Level of Dishonesty on Social Media (N=25)

Sl.No.	Level	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Very much	14	56
2	Much	06	24
3	Not Much	05	20
	Total	25	100.0

Source: Field survey, 2024

People tend to be very dishonest when using social media because it is their way of seeking validation. Some people may feel the need to present themselves in a certain way to gain approval from others in social media. They may also be dishonest because they fear being judged and critiqued by others.

Table 11. Opinion on effect of social media on people's perception of news

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	28	87.5	87.5	87.5
	No	04	12.5	12.5	100.0
	Total	32	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field survey, 2024

As shown in table, 87.5 percent of the respondents agree that social media has affected the way people perceive and respond to news and current events and only 12.5 percent of the respondent state that social media has not affected the way people perceive and respond to news and current events.

Table 12. Opinion Regarding Impact of Social Media on User's Health

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	25	78.1	78.1	78.1
	No	07	21.9	21.9	100.0
	Total	32	100.0	100.0	

Source: Field survey, 2024

Accordingly, 78.1 percent of the respondents believe social media has an impact on user's health. This suggests that social media is a widely believed factor affecting health. However, it is important to note that correlation does not necessarily imply causation. Apart from the basic causes of impact of social media on health, an in-depth research is needed to determine the specific ways in which social media use can impact health.

H1: There is an association between social media users and health impacts, is tested by crosstabulation of Table 4 and Table 12, using Chi-square test.

Figure 13. Social Media Users and Impact of Social Media on Health

		Impact of Social Media on Users Health		Total
		No	Yes	
Social Media Users	No	3	0	3
	Yes	4	25	29
Total		7	25	32

Figure 14. Chi-Square Tests

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (2-sided)	Exact Sig. (1-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	11.823 ^a	1	.001		
Fisher's Exact Test				.007	.007
Linear-by-Linear Association	11.453	1	.001		
N of Valid Cases	32				

Significance

Asymptotic Significance (2-sided): The p-value is 0.001, which is less than the commonly used significance level of 0.05.

*This suggests we can reject the null hypothesis i.e., H₀: There is no association between social media users and health impacts which accepts H₁: **There is significant association between social media users and health impacts.***

Interpretation

In simpler terms, the results provide strong evidence (p-value < 0.05) that there is a statistically significant association between the two categorical variables i.e., social media users and its health impacts in the analysis.

Opinion Regarding Cyber Bullying

Respondents stated that cyberbullying is a serious issue that can have harmful effects on individuals, especially young people. It can cause depression and even lead to self-harm or suicide in extreme cases. It also involves the use of technology to target individuals with harmful messages, or videos. Further stated, that cyber bullying can take forms of such as spreading rumours, sharing private information without consent, and creating fake accounts to impersonate someone. Cyberbullying occurs anonymously, making it difficult for victims to identify the perpetrator and seek help, it also has a long lasting impact on a persons reputation and social relationship affecting their self-esteem and confidence.

Suggestions to Prevent Cyber Bullying and Other Adversities of Social Media

1. Education and awareness: Teaching children, parents, and educators about the risk associated with social media and the dangers of cyberbullying and how to recognize and respond to prevent incidents from occurring.
2. Promote positive online behaviour: Encouraging empathy, respect, and kindness in online interactions can create a more positive digital environment and reduce risk likelihood.
3. Monitor online activity: Parents and educators should monitor children's online activity to identify any signs and take appropriate action.
4. Teach digital citizenship: Educating children about responsible online behavior, privacy settings, and the impact of their actions online can help prevent them from becoming victims or perpetrators.
5. Provide support and resources: Offering counseling services, hotlines, or support groups for victims can help them cope with the emotional effects of harassment.
6. Collaborate with technology companies: Working with social media platforms and tech companies to implement safety features, reporting mechanisms, and anti-bullying policies.

Conclusion

The present study entitled, “*Social media and social interaction: adversities and advantages with special reference to cyber bullying*”, is an endeavor to fulfill the objectives of studying the effects of social media on social interaction and its negative as well as positive impacts, where cyber bullying as one of the negative effect of social media is discussed at large to formulate recommendations. The research hypotheses are tested and research questions are fulfilled to achieve the research goals and to realise the potential risks associated with excessive use of social media.

Apart from the profile of the social media users, the research evident several advantages as well as adversities of using social media platforms. The positive impacts like enhanced information, career advancement and worldwide interaction with the people and also development of social contacts, Increase IQ level and fostering new relationship and strengthening existing ones and on the contrary the adversities includes waste of time and money, limits contact with relatives and friends, addiction and cyber bullying.

In order to reduce the negative impacts of using social media on social interaction and communication a number of recommendations can be followed such as, limiting the screen time, engaging in face-to-face interaction, practice mindful social media use and a balance between online and offline activities.

Conflict of Interest

No conflict of interest.

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